

Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology

Summary report of modelling work conducted in 2025

Authors: Peter Skelsey, Alon Zuta, Jacqui Brandt, Gaynor Malloch, Carolyn Mitchell, Ali Karley

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Summary

Data on Spotted Wing Drosophila (SWD) trap captures at the James Hutton Institute were integrated with habitat and weather data to investigate if pest abundance could be accurately predicted from local environmental conditions. Machine learning techniques were applied to the data to derive a classification model that can discriminate between low and high pest captures with an accuracy of 82%. Explainable AI techniques identified that the surrounding area of cereal and arable crops, woodlands, fruit crops, the annual mean temperature and area of artificial structures were the most important variables for accurate prediction.

Research questions

- (1) Can annual trap captures be accurately predicted using local habitat and weather variables?
- (2) What variables are the most informative for accurate prediction?

Data

SWD abundance data were collected from 12 traps within a 1 km area at the James Hutton Institute from 2016 to 2022. Trap captures were accumulated over each year to provide an annual capture per trap. The Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) database was used to derive 18 features (predictor variables) representing the areas of different agricultural land parcel types within a 100 m radius of each trap for each year of the study period. Satellite imagery was used to derive a further 4 non-agricultural linear land use features. The habitat data exhibited a high degree of sparsity, characterised by a large proportion of zero-valued features across observations. Consequently, the 22 habitat features were consolidated into 7 aggregated features by summing the areas of distinct land parcels. Data from the on-site weather station was used to derive a range of different bioclimatic features, representing long-term averages (within-season and between-season months and quarters, as well as annual averages) of temperature and precipitation. A summary of the full range of features available for the modelling and their acronyms is given in Table 1.

Methods

For research question 1, the prediction problem was reduced to its simplest formulation as a binary classification task, distinguishing low and high trap captures, with low captures defined as those less than or equal to the median annual trap capture and high captures as those exceeding the median. A suite of 7 machine learning classification algorithms, ranging in complexity, were applied to the data: naïve bayes, discriminant classifier, k-nearest neighbour, decision tree, support vector machine, neural network, and ensembles of classifiers. The models were trained, tuned, and tested using a repeated nested cross-validation (RNCV) procedure with Bayesian optimisation of hyperparameters. The dataset was small with many

predictors therefore a feature selection algorithm was employed within the RNCV to retain only the most salient variables; removal of uninformative features ensures the model has sufficient data to accurately estimate the effect of each feature and reduces model complexity, which improves predictive accuracy and interpretability. Selection of the six most significant features provided an appropriate level of dimensionality for the modelling task. The performance metrics used to evaluate the model on unseen (held-out) test data in the RNCV procedure were: true negative rate (TNR, the proportion of low captures that are correctly classified by the model), false negative rate (FNR, the proportion of instances where the model predicted low but the actual outcome was high), false positive rate (FPR, the proportion of instances where the model predicted high but the actual outcome was low), true positive rate (TPR, the proportion of high instances that are correctly classified by the model), positive predictive value (PPV, the proportion of instances classified as high that are truly high), negative predictive value (NPV, the proportion of instances classified as low that are truly low), and accuracy (the proportion of correct predictions).

For research question 2, the best performing algorithm was then retrained using all the data and interpreted using Shapley values to understand how it makes decisions and to identify which features were the most important for making accurate predictions.

Table 1 – Features used in the modelling

Habitat features		Bioclimatic features	
Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
ART	Artificial structures	BIO1	Annual mean temperature
BLR_OPEN	Blackcurrants grown in the open	BIO2	Mean diurnal temperature range
HOT	Hedgerows / line of trees	BIO3	Temperature seasonality
LAY	Lawns and yards	BIO4	Max. temperature of warmest month
PGRS	Permanent grassland	BIO5	Min. temperature of coldest month
RASP_OPEN	Raspberries grown in the open	BIO6	Temperature annual range
RG	Rough grazing	BIO7	Isothermality
SB	Spring barley	BIO8	Mean temperature of wettest quarter
SFB	Spring field beans	BIO9	Mean temperature of driest quarter
SO	Spring oats	BIO10	Mean temperature of warmest quarter
SP	Seed potatoes	BIO11	Mean temperature of coldest quarter
SPP	Spring protein peas	BIO12	Annual precipitation
UCAA	Uncropped arable land	BIO13	Precipitation of wettest month
WB	Winter barley	BIO14	Precipitation of driest month
WDG	Open woodland	BIO15	Precipitation seasonality
WOOD	Woodland	BIO16	Precipitation of wettest quarter
WOSR	Winter oilseed rape	BIO17	Precipitation of driest quarter
WW	Winter wheat	BIO18	Precipitation of warmest quarter
		BIO19	Precipitation of coldest quarter
		BIO20	Number of frost days
		BIO21	Number of consecutive frost days
		BIO22	Number of wet days
		BIO23	Number of consecutive wet days
Combined habitat features			
Acronym	Description		
Arable	Arable / fallow land		
Artificial	Structures, lawns and yards		
Cereals	Cereal crops		
Fruit	Fruit crops		
Grass	Grass, grazing, permanent cover		
Trees	Woodland, hedges, treelines		
Vegetables	Vegetable crops		

Results

There was marked variation in annual trap captures among traps and between years (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Total annual captures of Spotted wing drosophila at the James Hutton Institute site.

There was also marked variation in the amount of each habitat category across the whole JHI site, with cereals dominating and fruit areas largely absent until 2021-2022 (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – Total amount of each habitat category surrounding all SWD traps at the James Hutton Institute site.

Unbalanced two-way ANOVAs were conducted to assess significant differences in habitat variables across traps and years (Table 2). Interaction terms were omitted due to insufficient observations within factor level combinations to support its estimation.

Table 2 – Summary of two-way ANOVA results showing the number of habitat variables exhibiting significant differences across traps and years

Habitat	Source	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Arable	Trap	9.048e-03	16	5.655e-04	8.1690	<0.001
	Year	1.296e-03	6	2.161e-04	3.1210	0.008
Artificial	Trap	1.807e-04	16	1.129e-05	1.6900	0.061
	Year	4.914e-05	6	8.190e-06	1.2260	0.300
Cereals	Trap	3.428e-04	16	2.142e-05	0.9610	0.505
	Year	5.048e-04	6	8.414e-05	3.7730	0.002
Fruit	Trap	4.388e-04	16	2.743e-05	1.8090	0.041
	Year	3.574e-04	6	5.956e-05	3.9280	0.002
Grass	Trap	3.899e-04	16	2.437e-05	5.7130	<0.001
	Year	2.263e-05	6	3.772e-06	0.8840	0.510
Trees	Trap	4.773e-06	16	2.983e-07	1.4270	0.146
	Year	2.274e-06	6	3.790e-07	1.8120	0.105
Vegetables	Trap	1.165e-03	16	7.278e-05	46.7150	<0.001
	Year	2.610e-05	6	4.351e-06	2.7920	0.015

A support vector machine was the most accurate model (82%) of the seven algorithms tested (Table 3).

Table 3 – Performance of models for forecasting SWD trap capture class on unseen test data

Model*	TNR†	FNR	FPR	TPR	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
NB	0.68 (0.025)	0.09 (0.009)	0.32 (0.025)	0.91 (0.009)	0.77 (0.011)	0.89 (0.009)	0.80 (0.008)
DC	0.72 (0.007)	0.14 (0.005)	0.28 (0.007)	0.86 (0.005)	0.77 (0.006)	0.84 (0.006)	0.79 (0.003)
KNN	0.69 (0.024)	0.13 (0.008)	0.31 (0.024)	0.87 (0.008)	0.76 (0.016)	0.85 (0.011)	0.78 (0.013)
DT	0.67 (0.028)	0.05 (0.010)	0.33 (0.028)	0.95 (0.010)	0.76 (0.020)	0.93 (0.009)	0.81 (0.009)
SVM	0.70 (0.028)	0.07 (0.030)	0.30 (0.030)	0.93 (0.003)	0.78 (0.021)	0.92 (0.004)	0.82 (0.013)
NN	0.69 (0.094)	0.13 (0.074)	0.31 (0.090)	0.87 (0.070)	0.77 (0.038)	0.84 (0.050)	0.78 (0.041)
ENS	0.68 (0.029)	0.09 (0.004)	0.32 (0.028)	0.92 (0.003)	0.77 (0.024)	0.90 (0.005)	0.80 (0.015)

* The machine learning classifiers are NB = naive Bayes, DC = discriminant classifier, KNN = k-nearest neighbour, DT = decision tree, SVM = support vector machine, NN = neural network, ENS = ensemble of decision tree models.

† The metrics are TNR = true negative rate, FNR = false negative rate, FPR = false positive rate, TPR = true positive rate, PPV = positive predictive value, NPV = negative predictive value, and accuracy. The metrics are the average over test sets, and standard deviations are given in parentheses.

The high level of accuracy of the final model gives confidence in the results of the model interpretation analysis (Figs. 3 & 4).

Figure 3 – (a) Global feature importance plot, and (b) local explanation plot for the support vector machine, where the colorbar indicates the value of the feature for each individual observation.

Figure 4 – Shapley dependence plots for the support vector machine. The units of the habitat variables are square kilometers, whereas BIO1 is in degrees centigrade.

The global feature importance plot (Fig. 3a) averages the absolute Shapley values for all features across all observations and sorts them in order of decreasing importance. This revealed that the 6 most important features for accurate prediction of SWD abundance class were cereal, arable, wooded and fruit areas, the annual mean temperature, and non-natural (artificial) areas. The unexpectedly greater importance of cereals over wooded and fruit areas likely reflects the absence of fruit areas prior to 2021–2022 (Fig. 2) and the widespread presence of cereals, which may offer suitable vegetation in field margins.

Local explanation plots display Shapley values for individual observations, colour-coded by feature value. Positive Shapley values push the model towards a prediction of the ‘high’ abundance class whereas negative shapely values push the model towards a prediction of ‘low’. Local explanation plots therefore describe the dominant direction of association between feature and model outcome (Fig. 3b). Shapley dependence plots provide further insight by revealing the functional form of the relationship between feature values and model output (Fig. 4). The dependence plots show that cereal areas $>0.011 \text{ km}^2$, and arable, wooded, and fruit areas of 0.001 , 0.003 , and 0.001 km^2 respectively, increase the likelihood of high SWD abundance. In contrast, annual mean temperatures $<9.15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are associated with low abundance predictions.

Future work

In the coming year male and female captures will be analysed and modelled separately.

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